
**THE STUDY OF NATIONAL HORTICULTURE MISSION (NHM) SUBSIDY FOR
FLORICULTURE IN MAHARASHTRA (2006-07 TO 2014-15)**

Dr. Mrs. Sanhita Athawale

Professor & H.O.D (Banking) of T.J. College, Khadki

And

Maya Takalkar

Research Student of Ramakrishna More College, Akurdi

Abstract:

Floriculture is the discipline of Horticulture and the study of growing flowers plant. The study reveals that due to suitable soil and agro-climatic condition for flower cultivation there is tremendous scope for commercial floriculture in Maharashtra. Maharashtra state even though seventh in area stands third in terms of production in recent years the production in state has taken momentum due to subsidy policy of state government. The NHB and NHM are two important schemes provide subsidy to growers from planting material to post harvesting of flowers. The present paper discussed subsidy policy of National Horticulture Mission for floriculture development in Maharashtra.

Key words: *NHM, Subsidy, floriculture, cut flowers, loose flowers, bulbous flowers*

• Introduction:

Floriculture is a viable and profitable alternative for the new generation of farmers. This sector offers opportunities for generating income and employment, especially for women. By recognizing its full potential, India has a fair chance of attaining a strong position on the World floriculture platform. So Government of India have been taking various initiatives for development of floriculture. The Government has liberalized its policies to promote floriculture. The union government has recognized floriculture as a thrust area for export and announced several concessions/ incentives for its development in the country. The Government of India have set up various agencies and implementing various schemes for floriculture development in India.

Mission for Integrated Development of Horticulture (MIDH) is a centrally sponsored scheme for the holistic growth of the horticulture sector covering fruits, vegetables, root & tuber crops, mushrooms, spices, flowers, aromatic plants, coconut, cashew, cocoa and bamboo. MIDH have many sub-schemes and are of operation as NHM (National Horticulture Mission), HMNEH (Horticulture Mission for North East & Himalayan States), NHB (National Horticulture Board), CDB (Coconut Development Board), CIH (Central Institute of Horticulture). All schemes are working under roof of MIDH. Besides APEDA has initiated the various strategic measures, which have greatly enhanced the export performance of the floriculture industry and NABARD also has been playing important role in promoting and supporting hi-tech floriculture projects in different states, predominantly Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. NHM is one of the schemes provides assistance to the state and contributes greatly to floriculture development.

• National Horticulture Mission:

It was launched under the 10th five-year plan in the year 2005-06. The NHM's key objective is to develop horticulture to the maximum potential available in the state and augment production of all horticulture product. This is centrally sponsored schemes in which government of India shall provide 100% assistances to the State Mission during the 10th plan. During the 11th, the government of India assistances will be 85% with 15% contribution by the state government. Maharashtra is one of the leading flower producers in the country.

The state has varying soil and agro-climatic condition, which offer tremendous scope for commercial floriculture. Besides Floriculture crops are highly labour intensive and have the capacity to generate substantial direct and indirect employment in rural area as well as in urban area. Estimates across different states in India indicate that the employment generation of flower crops cultivation is higher than other horticulture crops, food crops and commercial crops. Thus recently Government of Maharashtra gives promotion to high quality and hi-tech floriculture. For development of horticulture including floriculture NHM provides subsidy for various components required floriculture development e.g. subsidy for hi-tech and general green house, shade net house, plastic tunnels and mulching paper with prescribed norms, subsidy for Post Harvest and Marketing Management is released for pack house, cold storage, Refer van/containers, pre-cooling unit, grinding and packing unit, contract farming, wholesale and retail market. In floriculture sector flower wise i.e. loose flowers, cut flowers, bulbous flowers subsidies are provided by NHM to farmers for above mentioned components required for floriculture developments. NHM is important step taken by government for floriculture development. Maharashtra state even though seventh in area stands third in terms of production in recent years the production in state has taken momentum due to subsidy policy of state government. Although Maharashtra has tremendous potential, infrastructure bottlenecks, absence of post-harvest management and other logistics acts as major constraints. It is only when policy can address these issues that the potential will be realised. Maharashtra is the second leading producer of Cut Flowers (11.5%) and ranked fourth in loose flowers (8.8%) in the country. This paper attempt to study NHM subsidy norms and subsidy releases for various flowers in Maharashtra from 2006-07 to 2013-14. The study of NHM achievements in terms of subsidy releases is important to evaluate NHM progress and improve its efficiency in implementation and development of floriculture in Maharashtra.

• Objectives

1. To study subsidy norms for various flowers in Maharashtra.
2. To study subsidy released for floriculture to farmers in Maharashtra.

• Data Source and Research Methodology:

This paper is based on secondary source of data. This research paper has been prepared by collecting information relating to subsidy releases and norms from target and achievement record of National Horticulture Mission Department of Maharashtra and NHM website of Maharashtra. Also Journals, government reports and internet source have been used for this paper. The period for the study has been considered from 2005-06 to 2013-14. The scope of study is limited to Maharashtra state. Simple tabular analysis and graphs have been used for presentation of paper.

• Subsidy Norms for flowers under National Horticulture Mission

There are different NHM subsidy norms for different types of flower i.e. Cut flowers, Bulbous flowers and Loose flowers etc.

1. Cut flowers

Cut flowers are flowers bud (often with some stem and leaf) cut from stalk as for making bouquet. Day by day demand of cut flowers is rising. There is tremendous market for cut flowers. There is wide scope to increasing the area of cut flowers in Maharashtra. The cut flowers like Rose, Gerbera, Carnation, Chrysanthemum, Aester, Bird of Paradise, Hellconias etc. will be promoted under this component.

2. Bulbous flowers:

Tuberose, gladiolus, lilies, lily am, callosity, delia, these are bulbous flowers which means plants growing from bulb. They are used as cut flowers and are promoted with cut flowers. They are grown for ornamental

purposes. The improved varieties of these bulbous flower crops are collected from different research stations and abroad and multiplied at Gov. Nurseries and given to farmers under this component.

3. Loose flowers

The flowers which are usually harvested without stalk and used for gajara, veni and Garland are categorized as loose flowers. Famous loose flowers are marigold, aster, gaillardia, shevanti, mogra, zinnia, jai-jui, bijali. For the production of these flowers, high quality planting material and imported seeds and plants are provided to flower growers under the programme. Following table 1. shows various subsidy norms for flowers under NHM.

Table.1-Subsidy norms for flowers under NHM

Sr No.	Types of Flowers crops	Norms of subsidy			
		2010	Max. Area (Ha)	2014	Max. Area (Ha)
1.	Cut flower	Rs.70,000/-	-	Rs.100,000/-	-
	Small Farmers	50% or Max 35,000/-	2	40% or Max 40,000/-	2
	Other Farmers	33% or Max 23.100/-	4	25% or Max 25,000/-	2
2.	Bulbous Flowers	Rs.90,000/-	-	Rs.1,50,000/-	-
	Small Farmers	50% or Max 45,000/-	2	40% or Max 60,000/-	2
	Other Farmers	33% or Max 29,700/-	4	25% or Max 37,500/-	2
3.	Loose Flowers	Rs.24,000	-	Rs.40,000	-
	Small Farmers	50% or Max 12,000/-	2	40% or Max 16,000/-	2
	Other Farmers	33% or Max 7,920/-	4	25% or Max 10,000	2

Source: N.H.M. (2014) Subsidy to Floriculture, Target and achievement

(Small farmers- having 1 to 2 ha. agriculture land holding)

Above table shows the subsidy norms for cut flowers, Bulbous and loose flowers under National Horticulture Mission during the year of 2010 and 2014. It is observed from the above table that subsidy norms available for various flowers under NHM have been revised from 2010 to 2014. The subsidy norms for cut flowers, Bulbous and loose flowers have been revised from Rs. 70,000, Rs.90000 and Rs. 24000 to Rs. 100,000, Rs.150000, Rs. 40000 in 2014 respectively. This shows that NHM have increased subsidy amount for floriculture from 2010 to 2014. It is also observed that NHM provides maximum financial assistance for bulbous flowers. While revising subsidy amount in 2014 maximum amount revised for bulbous flowers.

In 2010 one beneficiary could avail an assistance for maximum 2 ha. area in case of small farmers while it was 4 ha. area. for other famers but in 2014 it was revised to 2 ha.area for both small and other farmers. Though NHM gives priority to small farmers after2014 NHMbrought equality in maximum ha.area for all farmers while issuing subsidy.

• Achievement of National Horticulture Mission in Maharashtra.

N.H.M. gives subsidy to flower grower through District Superintendent Agriculture Officer (DSAO) in financial form. The objective of NHM is to give preference to small farmers (having land holding of 1 to 2 ha. Area) There is threefold classification to release subsidy i.e. cut flower, bulbous flower and loose flowers

• Subsidy to Cut Flowers

Cut flowers are promoted under the NHM programme for both controlled and open field.

Following table 2 shows the subsidy given by N.H.M. to cut flower grower during 2005-06 to 2011-12.

Table.2- Subsidy to Cut Flowers

Years	Small Farmers		Other Farmers		Total Fin (Lakh)
	Phy (ha.area)	Fin(Lakh)	Phy(ha.area)	Fin (Lakh)	
2006-07	300	20.84(68)	95	9.80(32)	30.65
2007-08	180	45.52(91)	31	4.25(27)	49.77
2008-09	10	12.05(73)	84	4.45(27)	16.50
2009-10	145	42.06(82)	43	9.52(18)	51.58
2010-11	142	42.00(71.32)	47	16.89(28.68)	58.89
2011-12	87	26.83(75.48)	37	8.75(24.62)	35.55
2012-13	127	35(80)	44	8.75(20)	43.75
2013-14	117	29.46(82.15)	23	6.40(17.85)	35.86
2014-15	85	9.32(59.09)	23	6.45(40.91)	15.77
Total	1,193	263.08(77.75)	427	75.26(22.25)	338.34

Source: N.H.M. Subsidy to Floriculture, Target and Achievement. (Figures in the bracket indicate percentage to respective total)

It is observed that small farmers have been disbursed subsidy of Rs.263.08 lakh (77.75%) for total 1,193 ha.area. while other farmers have been released subsidy amount of Rs.75.23 lakh(22.24%) for 427 ha.Area by N.H.M during the period of 2005-06 to 2012-13. It indicates that maximum amount disbursed to small farmers. If consider the entire amount average 80.19% amount released to small farmers.

• Subsidy to bulbous Flowers

Tuberose, gladiolus, lilies, lily am, callosity, delia, these are bulbous flowers which means plants growing from bulb. They are grown for ornamental purposes. For the promotion of such flowers research centres have been installed. Following table 3. shows the year wise subsidy released to bulbous flowers. table shows the year wise subsidy released to bulbous flowers. It is observed that total subsidy amount of Rs1200.23lakh (77.73%) issued to small farmers while other farmers received Rs.343.77lakh (22.27%) as subsidy. It can be observed that subsidy released equally to both small and other farmer category in year 2006-07; thereafter maximum subsidy has given to small farmer, eventually overall level average 75 per cent amount released to small farmers.

Table. 3: Subsidy to Bulbous Flowers

Years	Small Farmers		Other Farmers		Total Fin (Lakh)
	Phy (ha.area.)	Fin(Lakh)	Phy(ha.area)	Fin(Lakh)	
2006-07	240	116.65(50)	291	116.28(50)	232.93
2007-08	321	115.35(88)	86	15.80(12)	131.15

2008-09	506	254.43(82)	28	54.25(18)	308.68
2009-10	447	199.53(84)	131	38.58(16)	237.11
2010-11	412	182.43(83.24)	141	36.74(16.76)	219.17
2011-12	288	126.86(82.62)	90	26.68(17.38)	153.54
2012-13	192	83.56(75.68)	81	26.84(24.32)	110.4
2013-14	213	88.68(84.95)	54	15.71(15.05)	104.39
2014-15	60	32.74(71.75)	35	12.89(28.25)	45.63
Total	2679	1200.23(77.73)	937	343.77 (22.27)	1544

Source: N.H.M. Subsidy to Floriculture, Target and achievement..(Figures in the bracket indicate percentage to respective total)

• Subsidy to Loose Flowers

The flowers which are usually harvested without stalk and used for gajara, veni and Garland. Famous loose flowers are marigold, aster, gaillardia, shevanti, mogra, zinnia, jai-jui, bijali. For the production of these flowers, high quality planting material and imported seeds and plants are provided to flower growers under the programme.

Table.4: Subsidy to Loose Flowers

Years	Small Farmers		Other Farmers		Total Fin (Lakh)
	Phy(ha.area)	Fin(Lakh)	Phy(ha.area.)	Fin(Lakh)	
2006-07	892	99.20(63)	478	58.97(51)	158.17
2007-08	660	104.32(86)	208	16.53(14)	120.85
2008-09	747	123.83(80)	395	31.44(20)	155.27
2009-10	1026	121.83(80)	332	25.66(17)	146.98
2010-11	871	108.41(80.82)	318	25.72(19.18)	134.13
2011-12	726	86.13(80.18)	266	21.29(19.82)	107.42
2012-13	727	86.46(78.56)	277	23.6(21.44)	110.06
2013-14	378	49(68.27)	249	22.77(31.73)	71.77
2014-15	199	48.90(76.01)	126	15.43(23.99)	64.33
Total	6310	827.57(77.42)	2848	241.41(22.58)	1068.98

Source: N.H.M. Subsidy to Floriculture, Target and achievement. (Figures in the bracket indicate percentage to respective total)

It is observed that total subsidy amount of Rs.827.57(77.42%)lakh(75.43%) issued to small farmers while other farmers received Rs.241.41(22.58%)lakh by NHM. Above table.4 clarifies that NHM released subsidy to loose flower grower. It concluded after critical observation at overall level, average 77 per cent subsidy released to small-scale farmers, which means maximum amount released to promote small farmers for flower cultivation. It showed, initially 63 per cent amount released to small farmers while 37 per cent amount released to other farmers, thereafter ratio between small and other farmers has been almost 8:20 and overall level average was 77and 73 per cent respectively.

Following graph no.1 shows the total NHM financial subsidy (in lakh) issued for various flowers in Maharashtra from 2006-07 to 2014-15. It is observed from graph no.1that NHMsubsidy ismaximum for bulbous flowers followed by Cut flowers and it is lower for loose flowers. If we observed entire amount average almost 75% to 80% released to small farmers.

Graph No 1: Financial subsidy release to various flowers in Maharashtra

Following graph no.2 shows yearwise trend in NHM subsidy releases for flowers in Maharashtra. It is observed that NHM have been issuing subsidy at fluctuating rate from 2006-07 to 2014-15 for all 3 kinds of flowers.

• **Division wise NHM subsidy releases for floriculture development in Maharashtra.**

Floriculture provides scope of high income generation to farmers due to huge demand for flower in urban areas and presence of export market. There are highest number of poly house (1271) owned by small farmers for cultivation of flowers in Maharashtra. The districts like Pune, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Sangli, Kolhapur, Thane, Nagpur, Satara well known for flower cultivation. Pune district is supposed to be district of 'corporate hi-tech floriculture' while Kolhapur and Sangli are districts of small farmers-hi-tech floriculture and Nashik and Ahmednagar districts are known for 'open flower cultivation'. Table 5 shows the division wise total NHM subsidy releases for floriculture development in Maharashtra from 2007-08 to 2015-16 .

Table: 5 Division wise NHM subsidy releases from 2007-08 to 2015-16

Sr. No.	Division	Total NHM subsidy from 2007-08 to (2015-16)	
		Phy (area)	Fin(Lakh)
1.	Thane	1325.74	180.64
2.	Nashik	532.25	86.17
3.	Pune	2,819.6	727.57

4.	Kolhapur	619.62	182.13
5.	Aurangabad	603.62	139.14
6.	Latur	1752.33	293.06
7.	Amravati	1040.1	176.91
8.	Nagpur	1,655.74	327.97
	Total	10349	2113.59

Source: N.H.M. Subsidy to Floriculture, Target and achievement.

Table 5 shows the division wise total NHM subsidy releases for floriculture development Maharashtra from 2007-08 to 2015-16. It is observed from table 5 that Pune division has been highest (2,819.6 ha. area) while Nasik has been lowest (532.25) targeted area for issue of NHM subsidy for floriculture development in Maharashtra. In Pune district, the land holding patterns reveals that 80.5% of farmers have land holding below 2 hectares. Therefore cultivation of floriculture and horticulture provides opportunity to them to raise their income. This can be the reason that NHM has been issuing highest subsidy to Pune district. Also other supportive factors like Horticulture training Centre is set up in Talegaon Dhabhade for Training farmers in Green house management with special focus on floriculture, favourable climate, availability of other planting material, easy access to airport and market etc. are available for floriculture in Pune district.

• Problems in Maharashtra in floriculture Industry:

Although Maharashtra has tremendous potential, infrastructure bottlenecks, absence of post-harvest management and other logistics acts as major constraints which are as follows:

1. Need for procuring high quality planting material at high cost
2. Lack of information on varieties at demand in international market
3. Lack of knowledge about the obligations on specification among the producers/exporters
4. Inadequate technology support.
5. Non-availability of technically competent, manpower.
6. Non-existence of adequate post-harvest infrastructural facilities including cold system.
7. Lack of good packaging material.

It is only when policy can address these issues that the potential will be realised. Thus NHM has special and remarkable role in floriculture development in Maharashtra.

• Progress of NHM in Maharashtra:

The performance under all the component of NHM is good. Productivity & production of cut flowers has increased due to development of infrastructure facilities. The state has made good use of NHM scheme for development of infrastructure facilities

Progress of NHM till 2014-15:

1. NHM benefited to farmers in various way under HRD (Human resources Development) component of NHM. Total 1.65 lakh farmers have been trained for various horticulture activities.
2. There are highest number of poly house (1271) owned by small farmers for cultivation of flowers.
3. An area of 14804 ha has been covered under protected cultivation.
4. Under the component of post harvest Management 3958 units including packhouse, cold storage units, refrigerated vans, primary/mobile processing units, ripening chambers, pre cooling units attach to cold storages and mobile pre cooling units have been established.
5. 23 market infrastructures have been set up.

An amount of Rs. 1679.09 crore was released to state till 2014-15 against which an expenditure of Rs. 1110.43 crore has been reported. Following table no.6 shows statewise allocation of fund for NHM for the 2015-16

Table No. 6 State wise approved Allocation of fund for NHMfor 2015-16

Sr.No.	States	Approved allocation of fund for NHM (in crores) 2015-16
A.	NHM states	-
1.	Andhra Pradesh	143.00
2.	Bihar	57.00
3.	Chhatisgarh	160.00
4.	Goa	6.00
5.	Gujarat	167.00
6.	Haryana	143.00
7.	Jharkhand	90.00
8.	Karnataka	163.00
9.	Kerala	81.00
10.	Madhya Pradesh	102.00
11.	Maharashtra	205.00
12.	Odisha	115.00
13.	Punjab	92.00
14.	Rajasthan	110.00
15.	Tamilnadu	123.00
16.	Telangana	81.00
17.	Uttar Pradesh	80.00
18.	West Bengal	57.00
19.	Delhi	1.00
20.	Lakshadweep	1.00
21.	Andaman & Nicobar	5.00
22.	Puducherry	2.00
23.	Dadara & Nagar Haveli	1.00
	Total NHM states	1985.00

Source: N.H.M. Subsidy to Floriculture, Target and achievement

It is observed from table no.6 that among 23 NHM states highest fund (Rs. 205 crores) have been allocated to Maharashtra for implementation of NHM scheme. This shows that state has been using good use of NHM for development of horticulture activities and other related facilities through NHM subsidy policy.

• Conclusion

It is concluded that that maximum amount disbursed to small farmers through National Horticulture Mission. It means NHM is fulfilling its objective to prefer small farmers for issue of subsidy as NHM issue subsidy for 0.05 to 1 acreage area. The NHM made possible for small farmers to afford the establishment cost of greenhouse also cost of other required components like plastic tunnels planting material and mulching paper

with prescribed norms, subsidy for Post Harvest and Marketing Management is released for pack house, cold storage, Refer van/containers, pre-cooling unit, grinding and packing unit, contract farming, wholesale and retail market, training programme to farmers. This strategy of subsidy policy of NHM helps the small farmers to increase income. Diversification of other traditional crops into floriculture business has emerged as profitable one for small farmers due to NHM policy. Agriculture labourer also has increased as protected cultivation as well as open field cultivation of flower requires skill labours for various activities in greenhouse. The NHM have been issuing subsidy at fluctuating rate from 2006-07 to 2014-15. The prescribed subsidy amount of NHM is maximum for bulbous flowers and lower for loose flowers. While revising subsidy norms in 2014 it is observed maximum increment i.e. 60,000 prescribed for bulbous flowers and lower increment (16000) for Loose flowers. In 2010 one beneficiary could avail an assistance for maximum 2 ha. area in case of small farmers While it was 4 ha. area. for other famers but in 2014 it was revised to 2 ha. area for both small and other farmers. It means after 2014 NHM brought equality in norms of maximum ha. area for all farmers while issuing subsidy. Among all flowers the maximum subsidy (Rs1544lakh) has been provided for Bulbous flowers by NHM.

Division wise scenario of Maharashtra shows that Pune division has been highest (2,819.6 ha. area) while Nasik has been lowest (532.25 ha.) targeted area for issue of NHM subsidy for floriculture development in Maharashtra. State wise allocation of fund to NHM shows that among 23 states Maharashtra state have been allocated highest fund. Overall observation indicates that National Horticulture Mission have been Playing significant role in development of horticulture and floriculture in Maharashtra. Also NHM subsidy policy is important opportunity opened in favour of small farmers and marginal farmers.

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